

DETECTION OF EXHAUSTION IN TEA BY MEASUREMENT OF ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY

BY J. K. ROY AND S. N. MITRA

WEST BENGAL PUBLIC HEALTH LABORATORY, CALCUTTA

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Sophistication of tea is practised in various ways such as admixture with exhausted or spent leaves, foreign substances, sand and siliceous matter (in dust tea), excessive amount of hard, woody stalks and stems, etc. Amongst these, the use of exhausted or spent material is a common and an age-old method of adulteration. For its detection, determination of total and water-soluble ash and water extract is usually done. Estimation of these constituents, although of great value, is time consuming. Attention was therefore directed to finding out a rapid method of detection of exhaustion, which can be conveniently used as a routine sorting test in the analysis of tea. Also, such a test could be utilised as a check on the usual chemical values like ash, water extract, etc.

As electrical conductivity (or the specific conductivity) of a solution at a definite temperature depends on the nature and amount of electrolyte (soluble salts) dissolved, the electrical conductivity of the water infusion of a tea, prepared under the standard condition, may likely lead to a method which may give an idea of the genuineness of the sample with respect to exhaustion. Actually, exhaustion removed more or less the soluble salts from tea and lowered its electrical conductivity. In the present paper, the standard condition under which the conductivity has to be measured and the procedure to be followed are described in detail. Tentative standards for genuine, unexhausted tea are also given, which will help considerably the examination of this beverage.

EXPERIMENTAL

Tea samples of different brands (both leaf and dust varieties) were collected. The leaf tea was ground finely, and both the ground leaf tea and the dust tea were dried at 100°. In the dried materials, the total and water-soluble ash, water extract and electrical conductivity were determined.

Procedure

Total and water-soluble ash and water extract were determined by the usual methods¹⁻³.

Electrical conductivity.—Distilled water of conductivity less than 3 reciprocal megohm was used throughout this estimation.

Distilled water (300 ml.) was boiled in a 500 ml. beaker for 1 minute, and after removing the burner 1 g. of the ground dry sample was poured into the hot water. The contents of the beaker was stirred for half a minute with a glass rod and the tea was infused in hot water for exactly 5 minutes. The infusion was strained off from the residue with the aid of a suitable strainer admitting of rapid filtration, cooled to room temperature and made up to 500 ml. in a calibrated flask with distilled water. Conductivity of the infusion at 20° was determined by using an ordinary Dionic Water Tester. This apparatus is provided with a compensating device and records conductivity automatically at 20°.

Effect of exhaustion on the conductivity of tea.—Tea (10 g., in this case, the leaf tea was used *without* grinding) was extracted with 500 ml. of just boiled hot water for 5 minutes with occasional stirring to represent as far as possible the normal practise of making tea infusion; the water extract was drained off completely and the residue was thoroughly dried at 100°. In this exhausted tea, total and water-soluble ash, water extract and conductivity were determined by the procedure described above.

The effect of admixing varying proportions of exhausted tea with genuine samples on the values of total and soluble ash, water extract and conductivity, was also studied. In the end, the figures for the conductivity of genuine and exhausted teas, thus obtained, were applied to the examination of unknown random samples in order to see how far these compare with the values of the other constituents like total and soluble ash and the water extract. Some of the results are summarised in Tables I and II.

TABLE I
Comparative analytical figures of genuine and exhausted tea.

Sample No. and description.	Total ash.	*Water-soluble ash.	Aq. extract.	Conductivity at 20° (mho × 10 ⁻⁶)	Total ash.	*Water-soluble ash.	Aq. extract.	Conductivity at 20° (mho × 10 ⁻⁶)		
Leaf Tea	No. 1 Original	7.09%	57.8	41.2%	130.0	7.0%	55.7	41.2%	120.0	
	Exhausted	3.90	33.3	23.0	42.0	3.90	28.3	16.1	30.0	
	No. 2	Origr	6.88	59.0	40.0	128.0	6.90	52.2	43.2	120.0
		Exh.	3.80	31.6	22.0	40.0	3.70	26.8	14.3	32.0
	No. 3	Orig.	5.65	61.4	44.6	120.0	6.12	62.4	45.1	122.0
		Exh.	3.12	37.8	21.3	38.0	3.21	29.6	15.2	28.0
	No. 4	Orig.	6.50	63.4	42.0	129.0	7.42	51.4	40.5	118.0
		Exh.	3.96	34.0	21.3	45.0	3.52	31.3	13.6	30.0
	No. 5	Orig.	6.11	62.7	42.0	120.0	6.81	54.6	42.5	119.0
		Exh.	4.10	33.4	22.8	40.0	3.60	29.2	12.9	33.0
	No. 6	Orig.	7.42	59.3	44.8	132.0	6.52	55.8	39.4	120.0
		Exh.	4.80	31.3	24.0	42.0	3.60	31.7	15.4	31.0
	No. 7	Orig.	6.62	54.4	39.8	116.0	7.11	53.7	40.2	118.0
		Exh.	3.75	37.3	24.4	39.0	3.82	25.7	13.4	28.0

* % total ash. All results are on oven-dry basis.

TABLE II
Effect of exhaustion.

Sample No.	% Decrease by exhaustion in Leaf Tea.				% Decrease by exhaustion in Dust tea.			
	Total ash.	Soluble ash.	Aq. extract.	Conductivity.	Total ash.	Sol. ash.	Dust tea.	Conductivity.
1	45.0	42.4	44.2	68.0	44.3	49.2	60.9	75.0
2	44.8	46.4	45.3	68.8	46.4	48.7	66.9	73.3
3	44.8	38.4	52.2	68.3	47.5	52.6	66.3	77.0
4	39.0	46.4	49.3	65.1	52.6	39.1	66.4	74.6
5	32.9	46.7	45.7	66.7	47.1	46.5	70.0	72.3
6	35.3	47.2	46.4	68.1	45.0	42.6	61.0	74.2
7	43.4	31.4	38.7	66.4	46.3	52.1	66.7	76.3

DISCUSSION

From Table I it will be seen that on exhaustion, total and water-soluble ash, water extract and conductivity decrease significantly in leaf teas; more so in dust teas for the simple reason that the latter being in a fine state of division have a greater chance of parting with the soluble constituents than the leaf teas.

Interpretation of the results will be more clear from Table II which shows the percentage fall in each constituent on exhaustion. In case of leaf tea, the percentage decrease does not, in general, exceed 50 in total and soluble ash and water extract, but goes up to nearly 69 in conductivity. In fact, percentage fall in conductivity does not go below 65. In case of dust tea, the percentage decrease does not exceed 53 in total and water soluble ash and 70 in water extract. The percentage fall in conductivity, in this case, may go up to as high as 77. The greater percentage decrease in the different constituents in case of dust tea is understandable, because the product is in a more finely divided state. It will also be seen that on exhaustion the fall in conductivity, whether in leaf tea or dust tea, is more significant than the decrease in any of the other three constituents. For detecting evidence of exhaustion therefore, the conductivity value should be even more indicative than the other three constituents.

With a view to obtaining suitable limits for conductivity of genuine, unexhausted tea, many known genuine samples were examined for their conductivity and the range was found to be 110 to 135×10^{-6} mho with the average figure of 124×10^{-6} mho.

The conductivity test was then applied to the examination of unknown samples as well as those adulterated in the laboratory by admixture with varying proportions of exhausted tea. Some of the results are summarised in Table III.

TABLE III

	Total ash.	Water soluble ash as % total ash.	Aq. extract.	Conductivity at 20°.
A. Genuine leaf tea	6.60%	59.1	42.2%	125 mho $\times 10^{-6}$
B. Do adulterated with 10% exhausted tea leaf	6.34	57.4	39.5	117
C. Do adulterated with 20% exhausted tea leaf	6.10	55.4	37.1	108
D. Do adulterated with 30% exhausted tea leaf	5.82	53.3	35.1	98
E. Do adulterated with 50% exhausted tea leaf	5.30	48.1	30.1	82
Adulterated samples from local market :				
*No. 1 (Dust)	7.46	39.2	27.8	80
*No. 2 (Do)	7.31	41.0	27.5	80
No. 3 (Leaf)	5.90	40.7	25.0	75
No. 4 (Do)	5.80	39.9	25.2	76

* These two dust teas contained appreciable amount of sandy matter.

All results are on oven-dry basis.

It will be seen (sample No. B) that 10% adulteration with exhausted material lowers the values of all the four constituents, but not significantly enough as to detect definite evidence of exhaustion. However, with 20% adulteration (sample No. C) the results, although on border line, are suspicious, *i.e.*, the value of the water extract is on the low side and the conductivity has fallen just below the minimum limit of 110. In the examination of natural products having often wide range of variation in their composition, this limitation in their analysis could not be always avoided, particularly in border line cases, and no one single test should be relied upon for the correct opinion. In border line cases, opinion should be based on a number of tests, of which, in the present case, surely conductivity is one. With 30% adulteration (sample No. D) the matter becomes easier and the water extract and the conductivity are distinctly low, indicating definite evidence of exhaustion. In the four market samples (Nos. 1, 2, 3 and 4), the values of the soluble ash, water extract and the conductivity are so low that no doubt should arise as to the use of exhausted materials. The high total ash in the two dust teas (No. 1 and 2) is due to the presence of extraneous sandy matter.

In conclusion, it may be said that determination of electrical conductivity serves as an excellent rapid sorting test in the examination of tea, particularly with a view to detecting the use of exhausted material, which can be further corroborated by detailed analysis, *i.e.*, estimation of total and soluble ash and water extract. In the reverse way, where in border line cases the usual chemical values give rise to suspicion, this simple physical measurement may help considerably. Therefore, in the routine analysis of tea, conductivity measurement is a very useful new addition, requiring only a few minutes for its execution.

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S U M M A R Y

Measurement of electrical conductivity of tea infusion is a valuable means to detect the presence of exhausted material in tea which is a common form of adulteration. The conductivity at 20° of a genuine tea infusion, prepared under standard condition, lies between 110 and 135 with an average of 124×10^{-6} mho. Exhaustion or admixture with exhausted tea lowers this value.

Determination of conductivity has a distinct advantage over that of the usual chemical values like ash, water extract, etc., in that it is far more rapid (takes only a few minutes) than any of the other estimations done in the analysis of tea. Therefore, this determination can be used successfully as a routine sorting test.

R E F E R E N C E S

1. Nicholls, "Aids to the Analysis of Foods and Drugs," Baillier, Tindall and Cox, 7th. Ed. 1952, p. 269.
2. The Bengal Food Adulteration Act, 1919, Notification No. 1977 P.H., dated July 24, 1930.